

From Lecture-Centric to Learner-Centred: Digital Pedagogical Design for Active and Sustainable Learning in Large Engineering Classes

Reihaneh Aghamolaei, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5655-100X>.

School of Mechanical & Manufacturing Engineering, Dublin City University, Ireland,

Abstract

Large undergraduate engineering modules face persistent challenges related to student engagement, inclusivity, assessment scalability, and staff workload. These challenges are particularly pronounced in mathematically intensive subjects, where traditional lecture- and laboratory-based delivery models often struggle to support diverse learner needs at scale. This paper presents a digital redesign of a second-year engineering module at Dublin City University. The redesign reconceptualised the module as an integrated digital learning environment structured around a hub-based virtual architecture, modularised mini-lectures and hybrid physical-digital laboratories. Automated quizzes, online simulations, and rubric-based grading were employed to enhance feedback. Early evidence indicates improved attendance, higher median marks, increased pass rates, and positive student perceptions of organisation and accessibility. The paper reflects critically on the benefits and limitations of the approach and discusses its transferability to other large-class contexts.

Keywords: *Large-class pedagogy; Digital learning design; Active learning; Inclusive education; Scalable assessment; Engineering education.*

1. Introduction

The increasing prevalence of large class cohorts in higher education has intensified long-standing pedagogical challenges related to student engagement, inclusivity, assessment, and the sustainability of teaching practice. In STEM disciplines, and particularly in mathematically intensive engineering modules, these challenges are amplified by the abstract nature of the content, the need for extensive problem-solving practice, and the logistical constraints associated with laboratory-based learning.

Large-class teaching environments have historically relied on lecture-centric approaches, fixed pacing, and resource-intensive assessment practices. Such models often limit opportunities for interaction and personalised feedback, disadvantage students with diverse learning needs, and place disproportionate demands on academic staff (Mulryan-Kyne, 2010; Biggs & Tang, 2011; Gibbs & Jenkins, 2014). These challenges are particularly severe in mathematically intensive modules, where conceptual difficulty and rigid pacing can hinder student progression (Prince, 2004).

Student engagement and inclusivity are, therefore, central concerns in large-class pedagogy. Straits (2007) highlights the importance of structure, care, and perceived instructor presence in mitigating the anonymity commonly experienced by students in large lectures. Similarly, Iaria and Hubball (2008) argue that effective large-class teaching requires deliberate instructional design rather than scaled-up versions of small-class practices.

Active learning has been widely identified as an effective strategy for improving learning outcomes in large classes. A meta-analysis by Freeman et al. (2014) demonstrates that active learning approaches significantly increase student performance and reduce failure rates in STEM education, including in large enrolment contexts. However, implementing active learning at scale introduces practical challenges related to staffing, assessment, and resource availability. Laurillard (2012) argues that addressing these challenges requires pedagogical designs that embed interaction and feedback within scalable learning architectures rather than relying on ad hoc instructional techniques.

Digital and blended learning environments have increasingly been positioned as enablers of scalable active learning. Well-designed digital resources can enhance flexibility, support self-paced learning, and improve accessibility without diminishing academic standards (Garrison & Vaughan, 2008; Means et al., 2013). Evidence emerging from the COVID-19 pandemic further emphasises that digital delivery alone is insufficient; rather, intentional pedagogical design is required to support engagement, equity, and learning quality in large online and blended classes (Hodges et al., 2020; Smyth et al., 2021).

Assessment and feedback remain among the most persistent challenges in large-class contexts. Timely and meaningful feedback is a critical determinant of learning, yet is often

least achievable in large cohorts (Gibbs & Simpson, 2004). Recent studies have explored the use of automated assessment, online quizzes, and rubric-based grading to enhance scalability and consistency while maintaining alignment with learning outcomes (Nicol et al., 2014; Whitelock & Watt, 2008). More recently, inclusivity and sustainability have become increasingly prominent in discussions of large-class pedagogy. Universal Design for Learning provides a framework for designing learning environments that offer multiple means of engagement that are particularly relevant in large and heterogeneous cohorts (Rose et al., 2014; Ferguson et al., 2021).

This paper addresses this gap by presenting a case study of a digital redesign of Engineering Mechanics: Dynamics (MEC1000), a large second-year engineering module at Dublin City University. The objective of this work is threefold:

- (1) to demonstrate how a digital pedagogical design can support active learning, inclusivity, and sustainability in a large engineering cohort;
- (2) to describe the implementation of a hub-based digital learning architecture and scalable assessment framework tailored to large-class constraints; and
- (3) to evaluate early outcomes and reflect on the implications for large-class teaching practice (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Conceptual framing of the digital pedagogical redesign, illustrating the intersection of active learning, inclusivity, and sustainability.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 describes the teaching and learning context of the module. Section 3 outlines the design-level pedagogical approach underpinning the digital redesign. Section 4 details the assessment strategy developed for large cohorts. Section 5 reflects on implications for large-class practice and transferability, followed by future directions and concluding remarks.

2. Description of the Teaching/Learning Context

Engineering Mechanics: Dynamics (MEC1000) is a 5-credit Spring-semester undergraduate module delivered in the School of Mechanical and Manufacturing Engineering at Dublin City University. The module is taken by over 170 second-year engineering students and forms a core component of the programme curriculum. The subject matter is mathematically intensive and conceptually demanding, requiring sustained engagement with abstract principles, worked examples, and applied problem-solving.

Prior to the redesign, delivery relied primarily on face-to-face lectures, scheduled tutorials, and a limited number of physical laboratory sessions. As cohort size increased, this model became increasingly constrained by staff workload, limited laboratory capacity, and reduced opportunities for timely feedback. Attendance declined, and student performance was uneven, particularly among those requiring additional time or alternative learning pathways.

The redesign was implemented in 2025 with the explicit aim of addressing these scale-related challenges. The module was reconceptualised as an integrated digital learning environment capable of supporting active, inclusive, and sustainable learning practices at scale.

3. Design-Level Pedagogical Approach: Systemic Digital Redesign

The redesign of MEC1000 was guided by four interrelated pedagogical principles: active learning, inclusivity, sustainability, and scalability. Active learning was prioritised to shift students from passive content consumption towards sustained engagement with worked examples and practice-based tasks. Inclusivity was addressed through principles of Universal Design for Learning, ensuring that students could access material through multiple formats and progress at their own pace (various means of representation and engagement). Sustainability focused on aligning pedagogical ambition with staff capacity, while scalability required that all learning and assessment activities function effectively for a large cohort.

Figure 2: Student-facing view of the MEC1000 digital learning environment

3.1. Hub-Based Digital Learning Architecture

A central feature of the redesign was the restructuring of the module's virtual learning environment (Loop) into a clear hub-based architecture. Dedicated hubs were created for Learning Content, Problem-Solving, Online Laboratories, and External Resources. This structure aimed to reduce cognitive load, improve navigation, and make learning pathways explicit. Separating content acquisition from application allowed students to revisit concepts as needed and engage in deliberate practice without the pressure of synchronous pacing (Fig. 3).

Figure 3: Hub-based digital learning architecture of the MEC1000 module, integrating content, problem-solving, online laboratories, and external resources

3.3. Self-Paced Learning

Some of the lectures were replaced with short recorded mini-lectures focused on key conceptual thresholds and worked examples. These recordings enabled students to pause, replay, and review explanations, supporting self-regulation and deeper understanding. The modular structure of the content allowed students to progress through the material in manageable units, reinforcing learning through repetition and practice. The WileyPLUS multimedia learning platform was integrated into the Loop environment to provide interactive tutorials, solved examples, and virtual laboratories.

3.3. Reconfiguring Laboratory Learning at Scale

Limited physical laboratory capacity represented a major constraint in the original module design. To address this, approximately two-thirds of the traditional laboratory sessions were replaced with interactive online simulations. These simulations were integrated with an AI-powered quiz generator developed in collaboration with the DCU Teaching Enhancement Unit, enabling students to engage with experimental concepts and receive immediate formative feedback. This hybrid physical-digital laboratory model ensured equitable access while reducing dependence on resource-intensive physical labs.

3.4. Assessment Design for Large Cohorts

Assessment design was central to the success of the redesigned module. In large engineering cohorts, traditional assessment approaches often strain staff capacity, delay feedback, and raise concerns about consistency and fairness. To address these issues, assessment in MEC1000 was redesigned as an integrated component of the digital pedagogical system.

AI-powered quizzes linked to online laboratory simulations were introduced to assess conceptual understanding and application rather than rote memorisation. Automated question generation enabled the creation of multiple equivalent assessment instances, reducing the risk of academic misconduct while maintaining fairness. Immediate feedback supported learning through reflection and self-correction.

Rubric-based automated grading was implemented for laboratory report writing. Clearly articulated criteria enhanced transparency and consistency, while significantly reducing marking workload and improving feedback turnaround times. The assessment framework offered multiple pathways for demonstrating learning, aligning with inclusivity principles and supporting the sustainability of delivery at scale.

4. Design-Level Pedagogical Approach: Systemic Digital Redesign

The impact of the digital redesign of MEC1000 was evaluated using a combination of quantitative performance indicators, student feedback, and staff observations. Consistent with practice-based research in large-class pedagogy, the focus was on early evidence of engagement, learning outcomes, and sustainability rather than on controlled experimental comparison (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: Overview of the pedagogical transformation resulting from the digital redesign.

Following implementation, average attendance increased from approximately 40% to 65%. Median assessment marks increased by 24%, rising from 51 to 63.3, while overall pass rates reached 86%, representing the highest recorded performance for the module in more than a decade. Improvements in attendance and performance are consistent with findings in the literature indicating that structured, flexible learning environments can mitigate

disengagement commonly observed in large lecture-based modules (Straits, 2007; Iaria & Hubball, 2008).

Student feedback further supports these quantitative trends. In end-of-module surveys, students described the module as “very well organised” and “easy to follow,” highlighting the value of a clearly structured digital environment that enabled learners to progress at their own pace. The ability to revisit worked examples, engage with short recorded explanations, and practise problem-solving independently aligns with prior research emphasising the importance of care, structure, and perceived instructor presence in large-class settings (Straits, 2007).

Beyond performance metrics, the redesign contributed to improved inclusivity by offering multiple pathways for engagement and assessment. The diversification of learning activities and assessment formats reflects core principles of Universal Design for Learning, particularly the provision of multiple means of engagement and representation (Rose et al., 2014). Such approaches have been shown to support participation and motivation in large and heterogeneous cohorts, where uniform instructional strategies often fail to meet diverse learner needs (Iaria & Hubball, 2008).

The integration of asynchronous learning resources and equivalent online laboratory activities further enhanced accessibility. Students were able to engage with module content regardless of physical laboratory access or timetable constraints. This aligns with evidence from large-class online and blended learning contexts, where flexibility and coordination of virtual activities have been shown to support engagement and experiential learning at scale (O’Connor et al., 2021).

From a sustainability perspective, the redesigned module embodies principles of Education for Sustainable Development by promoting learner autonomy, self-regulation, and efficient use of digital resources. The reduction in reliance on physical laboratory infrastructure and the use of scalable digital assessment tools contributed to a more sustainable model of delivery, both pedagogically and operationally. These outcomes are consistent with research highlighting the role of educational practices in modelling sustainability and systems thinking within higher education (Ferguson et al., 2021).

5. Reflection and Implications

The redesign of MEC1000 illustrates how system-level digital pedagogy can address persistent challenges in large-class engineering education. The improvement in engagement suggests that autonomy and self-paced learning are critical substitutes for individualised instruction in large cohorts. The diversification of learning and assessment pathways enhanced inclusivity and addressed equity concerns often magnified at scale.

Digital Transformation for Active, Inclusive, and Sustainable Learning in a Large Engineering Module

From a sustainability perspective, the integration of automated assessment and structured digital resources enabled staff to balance educational quality with realistic workload constraints. However, the approach required substantial upfront investment and careful oversight of AI-supported assessment tools, highlighting the importance of institutional support structures.

Crucially, the underlying design principles are transferable beyond engineering to other large STEM and non-STEM contexts. Framing digital transformation as pedagogical infrastructure rather than technological enhancement provides a practical model for improving large-class teaching.

Future iterations of the module will integrate learning analytics dashboards to monitor engagement patterns and further refine inclusivity. The digital structures, AI-quiz templates, and assessment rubrics will be disseminated as open educational resources within the PHELC community. The approach will also inform the redesign of other foundational engineering modules, contributing to institutional teaching strategies and alignment with the UNESCO Education for Sustainable Development 2030 framework.

References

- Biggs, J., & Tang, C. (2011). *Teaching for quality learning at university* (4th ed.). Open University Press.
- Ferguson, T., Roofe, C., & Cook, L. D. (2021). Teachers' perspectives on sustainable development: The implications for education for sustainable development. *Environmental Education Research*, 27(9), 1343–1359. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2021.1921113>
- Freeman, S., Eddy, S. L., McDonough, M., Smith, M. K., Okoroafor, N., Jordt, H., & Wenderoth, M. P. (2014). Active learning increases student performance in science, engineering, and mathematics. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 111(23), 8410–8415. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1319030111>
- Garrison, D. R., & Vaughan, N. D. (2008). *Blended learning in higher education: Framework, principles, and guidelines*. Jossey-Bass.
- Gibbs, G., & Jenkins, A. (2014). *Teaching large classes in higher education: How to maintain quality with reduced resources*. Routledge.
- Gibbs, G., & Simpson, C. (2005). Conditions under which assessment supports students' learning. *Learning and Teaching in Higher Education*, 1, 3–31.

- Hodges, C., Moore, S., Lockee, B., Trust, T., & Bond, A. (2020, March 27). The difference between emergency remote teaching and online learning. *EDUCAUSE Review*.
<https://er.educause.edu/articles/2020/3/the-difference-between-emergency-remote-teaching-and-online-learning>
- Iaria, G., & Hubball, H. (2008). Assessing student engagement in large and small classes. *Transformative Dialogues: Teaching and Learning Journal*, 2(1), 1–8.
<https://doi.org/10.59236/td2008vol2iss1751>
- Laurillard, D. (2012). *Teaching as a design science: Building pedagogical patterns for learning and technology*. Routledge.
- Means, B., Toyama, Y., Murphy, R., Bakia, M., & Jones, K. (2013). The effectiveness of online and blended learning: A meta-analysis of the empirical literature. *Teachers College Record*, 115(3), 1–47. <https://doi.org/10.1177/016146811311500307>
- Mulryan-Kyne, C. (2010). Teaching large classes at college and university level: Challenges and opportunities. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 15(2), 175–185.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13562511003620001>
- Nicol, D., Thomson, A., & Breslin, C. (2014). Rethinking feedback practices in higher education: A peer review perspective. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 39(1), 102–122. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2013.795518>
- O'Connor, C., Mullane, K., & Luethge, D. (2021). The management and coordination of virtual teams in large classes: Facilitating experiential learning. *Journal of Management Education*, 45(5), 739–759. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1052562921995550>
- Prince, M. (2004). Does active learning work? A review of the research. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 93(3), 223–231.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2168-9830.2004.tb00809.x>
- Rose, D. H., Gravel, J. W., & Gordon, D. T. (2014). Universal design for learning. In L. Florian (Ed.), *The SAGE handbook of special education* (2nd ed., pp. 475–489). SAGE Publications.
- Smyth, S., Buckley, K., Farrell, A. M., Glynn, M., Lowney, R., & Stone, S. (2021). The opportunities and challenges of emergency remote learning for large class students during the COVID-19 pandemic. In *Proceedings of Pedagogy for Higher Education Large Classes 2021*.
- Straits, W. (2007). “She’s teaching me”: Teaching with care in a large lecture course. *College Teaching*, 55(4), 170–175.

Digital Transformation for Active, Inclusive, and Sustainable Learning in a Large Engineering Module

Whitelock, D., & Watt, S. (2008). Reframing e-assessment: Adopting new media and adapting old frameworks. *Learning, Media and Technology*, 33(3), 151–154.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/17439880802447391>